

Spatio-Textual Regions: Extracting Sense of Place from Spatial Narratives

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Sense of place is a critical concept underlying the meanings attached to locations and locales in geography and related fields. This concept is often ambiguous and complex when presented in narrative text and challenging to represent and analyse at scale. Mapping a sense of place in this regard requires more than finding geographical coordinates or drawing polygons around toponyms. Our paper develops the concept of a spatio-textual region (STR), a method for identifying spatial clusters embedded in spatial narrative texts and explores the potential for mapping the results. We demonstrate the method on an 1857 publication by Thomas Nelson & Sons, a traveller's guide to the Lake District in England. We envision that this method could be employed at scale for generating novel representations of the sense of place embedded in tourist literature, personal journeys, and other spatial narratives.

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1 Representing Sense of Place

Sense of place is central to our identity as social creatures, but for all its importance, its definition is complex and multifaceted, and often nebulous and ambiguous. Geographers frequently view 'sense of place' as the third leg of a triad along with location (the coordinates of place), and locale (the physical attributes and activities surrounding these coordinates; Agnew, 1987). Sense of place lacks the precision of the first two attributes. It is 'the experiential and expressive ways places are known, imagined, yearned for, held, remembered, voiced, lived, contested and struggled over' (Feld and Basso, 1996). It exists at various scales, at times simultaneously. It may be positive (joy) or negative (fear; Tuan 1979).

Place has not been extensively considered in a narrative context. Franzosi (2010) discusses how narratives can be analysed quantitatively. He defines narratives as a series of events that make up the story the writer is telling along with evaluations or justifications as to why the events matter. He also notes that narratives consist of both process – what happens – and stasis – what exists. The implication is that a narrative is a series of events that occur in place and in which the place is either fundamental to the event, in which case it is part of process, or forms the background to it as stasis. Despite this, Franzosi does little to identify how place can be analysed as part of the narrative. More recently, Franzosi (2022) presents more detailed consideration of place in narrative largely focussing on place as one of what he terms the '5Ws + H': who, what, when, where, why, and how.

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Rajala et al. (2020) identify four major research needs to improve understanding of sense of place and its capacity in social-ecological research, one of which is central to this project: quantitative methods that can assess place constructs across larger samples and geographical areas. Also important are place ontologies. Ballatore (2016) presents a formalization of place ontologies from the perspective of ontology engineering, rather than philosophical ontology. Acknowledging the cultural dependency of place, he argues that such an ontology should be seen as a module positioned between foundational and domain ontologies whose deployment would increase the interoperability of datasets, particularly in the context of Linked Data. Our larger project both concerns itself with operationalizing these integrated conceptualizations of place and developing scalable methodologies that are widely applicable.

From a GIScience perspective, there have been many calls to improve the handling of place (see, e.g., Bergman and Lally, 2021; Gao, 2022; Purves et al., 2019; Tang and Painho, 2021). Hamzei et al. (2020) provide a review of how place is handled in the GIScience literature. They sub-divide place into a range of geographical and anthropocentric facets. Geographical facets include name, type, and location, while the anthropocentric facets expand sense of place to include the sense or spirit of place, place identity, place meaning, the activities that occur there, and the affordance or purposes that the place can be used for. Many GIScience-based studies have analysed user-generated content to define how place is represented. For example, Bahrehdar and Purves (2018) use tags from Flickr images to characterize places within London, Chesnokova and Purves (2018) use Geograph images to look at the experience of sound in Britain and Ireland, and Karimi et al. (2022) use TripAdvisor to study place in New York. There has been less research exploring place as represented in narratives. Donaldson et al. (2017) explore spatial clusters associated with individual search-terms such as ‘beautiful’ and ‘sublime’ in a corpus of writing about the English Lake District, while Paterson and Gregory (2018) use a larger selection of search terms to explore the geographies of poverty as represented in two British newspapers. Meanwhile, cartographers have used a range of techniques to represent sense of place and narrative, including through novel projections, photographic collage, layerings, typography, and annotation (Pearce, 2008; Solnit, 2010). These ‘alternative’ representations overcome some the conceptual and technical limitations imposed by digital spatial data infrastructures, but they remain challenging to scale and interpret analytically.

A multidisciplinary ESRC-NSF-funded Spatial Narratives project, housed at Lancaster University (UK), is developing ways to address these fundamental problems from computational, analytical, and representational angles. Recognizing that texts offer the most stable and traceable expressions of senses of place, the project uses Natural Language Processing (NLP) with Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to extract spatial information corpora of spatial narratives. We aim to draw on and extend work in GIScience on textual processing using geoparsing (Gregory et al., 2015) and machine learning (Karimi et al., 2022) to identify and extract spatial information derived from toponyms, geonouns, spatial prepositions, and temporal vocabularies.

For this paper, we focus on a narrow but novel approach to analysing extracted toponyms from narratives to demonstrate a potential way to map sense of place. We take for our example *The Corpus of Lake District Writing*, a collection of 80 richly descriptive texts¹ written about the English Lake District over two centuries. In previous work, we have mined this corpus to look at place using individual toponyms and the sense of place found in words in close textual proximity to them (Taylor and Gregory, 2022). These were aggregated to form spatial clusters of toponyms described as, e.g., ‘beautiful’ or ‘sublime’ (Cooper et al., 2016) but without regard to narrative context or more complex ideas of sense of place. This approach provided us a foundation on which we build the present analysis.

2 Spatio-Textual Regions

We propose here the concept of a spatio-textual region (STR) to identify cultural regions, or places, described by texts. An STR is a clustered set of toponyms and a contiguous section of text describing those toponyms. Spatial narratives include information about place in several forms: locational and distance metrics, events and material attributes, and sentimental qualities associated with those locations. Thus, an STR is conceived as a spatial and textual frame for Agnew’s location, locale, and sense of place characteristics (Agnew, 1987).

Our demonstration of this STR approach begins with a single text by Thomas Nelson & Sons entitled *The English Lakes* (Nelson, 1857), a traveller’s guide to the Lake District of around 10,000

Spatial Clusters by Paragraph

The English Lakes (1857), Thomas Nelson & Sons

Figure 1: Number of toponyms in each spatial cluster by paragraph. The x-axis shows the standardized paragraph position (0-100%) along the narrative sequence with the first paragraph on the left and last paragraph on the right.

words. Toponym extraction (geoparsing) is a prerequisite to this method, for which we use tools developed by our project team (Ezeani et al., 2023). Due to the complex nature of geographical names, automated geoparsing is not comprehensive or without error; we acknowledge but do not address these issues in the current work. This proposed approach also has two other key limitations: it is limited to point-based spatial data and is applicable only to corpora comprising a comparable extent and scale.

2.1 Spatial Clustering

After geoparsing a text, the first step in identifying an STR is to apply a spatial clustering algorithm such as k -means clustering to extracted coordinates. For a test case in Nelson, we identified eight major clusters corresponding to generally recognized Lake District areas (Grasmere, Cockermouth, Coniston, Pooley Bridge, Skiddaw, Windermere, Buttermere, and Keswick). Locations beyond the Lake District were excluded from the k -means clustering and allocated to their own separate ‘outside region’ cluster (Figure 1).

2.2 Textual Clustering

Raw spatial clustering ignores the structure or sequence of the narrative source and thus omits critical information about the unfolding of a spatial experience depicted by the author. In the next step, we identify each occurrence of each toponym by paragraph, and allocate it to its spatial cluster (Figure 1), thus illustrating how Nelson’s descriptions proceed through the Lake District from the beginning to the end of his text.

The English Lakes starts by using toponyms that are primarily in the northeastern area of the Lake District, around Penrith and Pooley Bridge (green). After 10% of the text, the guide begins to use some toponyms from the central area around Grasmere (orange), while continuing to describe sites in the northeast region. The text then moves to describe the southeastern area around Windermere (pink) and the southwestern area of Coniston (blue), before moving to the north in Keswick (purple) and eventually to the northwest area around Buttermere (brown). Figure 1 also shows that it is unusual to have a section of several paragraphs consisting of toponyms from only one cluster. Some paragraphs contain many toponyms while others have none. Finally, it is not always clear which spatial cluster is the focus, e.g., at a quarter of the way through the text; the guide apparently references toponyms in all major regions of the Lake District.

In practice, textual descriptions that include locations may be near each other geographically or referentially, i.e., by recalling a memory or imagining a distant place. Smoothing helps to define continuous sections of text that refer *primarily* to a particular spatial cluster of locations, even if it contains toponyms from elsewhere. We chose a simple method of giving each toponyms a smoothed

Spatio-Textual Regions

The English Lakes (1857), Thomas Nelson & Sons

Figure 2: Spatio-textual regions in Nelson's 1857 text. The major STRs are outlined manually to indicate their *approximate* spatial extent.

cluster ID corresponding to the most common spatial cluster among its eight neighbors in the text, and then identifying breaks by comparing smoothed and original cluster IDs.

Spatio-textual regions (STRs) were created by working through the smoothed clusters in textual order. The first toponym, for instance, is allocated to the first STR (in our example, the area around Penrith and Patterdale). For subsequent toponyms a new STR is defined if both the smoothed cluster ID and the original cluster ID for this toponym were different from the smoothed cluster ID of the previous toponym. Finally, we enforce that a new STR cannot be defined mid-paragraph. This allows us to reflect the importance of paragraph structure to textual descriptions and aligns with other paragraph-level textual analysis methods.

2.3 Representing Place

When combined, the spatial and textual clustering approach allows us to map STRs, or *places*, derived from the corpus, thereby combining both locational information with the rich sense of place information embedded in narratives. By mapping the spatial loci and narrative progression of the STRs (Figure 2), distinctive places begin to take shape for Nelson. For example, Windermere emerges as both spatially and narratively distinct from adjacent Ambleside, while other authors may disagree. Overlapping STRs indicate geographical areas that the guide repeatedly returns to, even if only referentially at a distance. Indeed, the guide instructs in the Grasmere area: 'From this walk many charming views may be had of the scenery around Rydal Lake, which is eminently beautiful.'

STRs both define an approximate spatial extent and section of narrative. Once STRs are defined, the narrative can then be examined with sentiment analysis or other textual methods. For this phase of the work, we adopted a basic approach to sentiment evaluation, which relies on a pre-prepared

Sentiment by narrative sequence and STR

The English Lakes (1857), Thomas Nelson & Sons

Count of positive and negative words per paragraph

Figure 3: Sentiment by narrative sequence and spatio-textual regions in Nelson's 1857 text. Regions differ in their positive, negative, and total sentiment, with the peak emotions appearing in the central portion of the text (and space, see Figure 2).

sentiment lexicon (Hu and Liu, 2004)² Figure 3 shows the relative strength of positive or negative sentiment by paragraph and each STR in Nelson's text.

This analysis provides a measure of how positively the writer responds to each place by showing the per paragraph density of positive and negative terms (average count of positive and negative words per paragraph). On average, positive words outweigh negative ones by a factor of two, yet there are clear differences in how Nelson responds to different places in different parts of the text. For example, Nelson's description of Ambleside is associated with positive sentiment, while Keswick and Borrowdale are more neutral.

3 Comparative Analysis

We expect the techniques described above can be effective at identifying STRs in a range of travel and other spatial narratives such as those found in the texts of our Lake District corpus. Our larger goal is to generalize these methods to investigate corpus-level patterns. Each author in the Lake District corpus narrates a unique spatial and narrative sequence, defining STRs unique to their perception. A comparative analysis of convergent and divergent STRs across authors thus reveals the varied distinctive regions and itineraries embedded in Lake District texts. We can thus begin to answer the question of whether there are dominant STRs or sequences of STRs in geospatial or textual terms. Do STRs tend to be consistent across authors? Do texts narrate STRs in a consistent sequence? Do different regions have distinctive sentimental qualities depending on the author?

Figure 4 presents evidence from five texts in the corpus evaluating this approach at a small scale. For demonstration purposes, a single distinctive STR was chosen for its spatial contiguity and distinctive sentimental qualities. Each of these STRs was selected on the basis of a combination of highly distinctive features – both textual and geographical. Notably, across five authors, we see spatially separate STRs emerge, and their descriptions capture the unique sense of place qualities of those places at the time the texts were written, according to the individual perspectives of the five authors. Such a literary map of the Lake District evokes the process of how places are both described and constructed through these texts. One could imagine extending this comparative approach by examining STRs that emerge for a single geographical region across multiple authors, or considering in more depth the sequencing of STRs (e.g., Figure 2) in space and text and the role this may play in accounting for differing experiences of place.

Distinctive Spatio-Textual Regions by Author

Most frequent positive and negative sentiment words by STR

Positive sentiment words

Negative sentiment words

Figure 4: STRs in a comparative perspective: distinctive STRs by author. STRs are defined by choosing one spatially and textually distinct region for each author.

4 Conclusion

This paper reports on initial progress toward a simple but effective method of identifying the spatial and textual extents and qualities of places described in travel narratives. We propose the concept of spatio-textual regions (STRs) and explore their characteristics in a corpus of Lake District travel writing. Within individual texts, the sense of movement through, observation, and experience of place emerges from a combination of textual analysis and geography. The ebb and flow of the sense of place in a narrative can be observed in this example with high and low points of emotional response. When viewed from the perspective of several texts, distinctive STRs can be mapped and contrasted, and the sequential and spatial similarities of STRs can be compared. While limitations to this approach are noted, the research has broader application to other corpora. In our own work, we anticipate applying these methods to an equally rich set of oral testimonies of Holocaust survivors. Using similar methods, it will be possible to explore platial dimensions of memory in this corpus, enriching our understanding both of individual experience and collective patterns forged in this radically different context.

Notes

1. <https://github.com/UCREL/LakeDistrictCorpus>
2. <http://www.cs.uic.edu/~liub/FBS/sentiment-analysis.html>

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Author Contributions

I Gregory originated the concept of STR. E Steiner and Z Frank contributed to the concept and text analysis. I Ezeani performed text extraction and sentiment analysis. D Bodenhamer and I Gregory drafted the text, E Steiner and Z Frank finalized the text. E Steiner developed the figures.

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